

A VOXEL-BASED HOMOGENIZATION TECHNIQUE FOR THE UNIT CELL THERMOMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A voxel-based homogenization technique for predicting how a textile reinforced composite will warp during manufacture is outlined. An approach is detailed involving the finite element analysis of a unit cell, based upon a textile geometric model, and good agreement with experimental data is shown.

Keywords: woven, fibre reinforced, composites, elastic, thermoelastic, thermomechanical, unit cell, representative volume element

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their good mechanical performance, woven composites are being ever more widely used in manufacturing, with applications including the production of automotive and aircraft components. In order to produce a part of a given shape and size, it is necessary to be able to predict how such materials warp during manufacture. To this end, unit cells or representative volume elements (RVEs, small repeating blocks) of laminae of them are analyzed.

The approach developed here is to generate a geometric model of the RVE using the Tex-Gen software [1], partition the RVE into voxels (brick elements), and model the composite as being homogeneous in each voxel. Each voxel is subdivided into cuboids, the effective thermomechanical properties of the material in each subcuboid are determined micromechanically (further sampling within the subcuboid gives the fibre volume fraction), and averaging is used to find the effective properties of the material in the voxel.

To approximate the thermomechanical properties of the bulk composite, a series of finite element analyses (FEAs) are used to find the response of the cell of the effective material to normal and shear strains and uniform temperature changes under suitable periodic boundary conditions.

The concept of voxel-based meshing has its origins in image processing, and is summarized in the current context in [2]. As in [3], homogenization is applied at two length-scales. Firstly, it is assumed that an individual laminate can be divided into a number of identical, repeating RVEs; and secondly it is assumed that, at any point in a yarn, the fibre reinforcement can be considered to be locally unidirectional.

The voxel based discretization of the RVE and determination of the thermomechanical properties of the bulk composite are discussed in Section 2, and validation for a plain weave carbon/epoxy composite is provided in Section 3.

2. THERMOMECHANICAL MODELLING

The discretization of the RVE is discussed in Section 2.1, the determination of the effective thermomechanical properties of the material in each voxel is considered in Section 2.2, and the subsequent determination of the effective thermomechanical properties of the bulk material is examined in Section 2.3.

2.1 The Voxel-Based Discretization of the RVE

Consider an RVE $[x_b, x_t] \times [y_b, y_t] \times [z_b, z_t] \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ of a lamina of a textile reinforced composite (Figure 1(a)). This is discretized into $N = N_x N_y N_z$ voxels with vertices

$$x_i = x_b + ih_x, \quad y_j = y_b + jh_y, \quad z_k = z_b + kh_z, \quad 0 \leq i \leq N_x, \quad 0 \leq j \leq N_y, \quad 0 \leq k \leq N_z,$$

(see Figure 1(b)) where the mesh sizes are given by

$$h_x := \frac{x_t - x_b}{N_x}, \quad h_y := \frac{y_t - y_b}{N_y}, \quad h_z := \frac{z_t - z_b}{N_z}.$$

Figure 1: (a) A typical RVE (geometrical model of a 5-harness satin from TexGen), and (b) the discretization of the RVE into $5 \times 4 \times 3$ voxels.

2.2 The Effective Thermomechanical Properties of the Material in a Voxel

The subdivision of a voxel into cuboids is discussed in Section 2.2.1, the determination of the effective thermomechanical properties of the material in each subcuboid is detailed in Section 2.2.2, and the use of these properties to find the effective properties of the material in the voxel is considered in Section 2.2.3.

2.2.1 The Subdivision of a Voxel into Cuboids

The voxel $V_{i,j,k} := [x_i, x_{i+1}] \times [y_j, y_{j+1}] \times [z_k, z_{k+1}]$ ($0 \leq i < N_x$, $0 \leq j < N_y$, $0 \leq k < N_z$) is subdivided into $N_v = N_x^v N_y^v N_z^v$ cuboids whose vertices are given by

$$x_{i,l} = x_i + lh_x^v, \quad y_{j,m} = y_j + mh_y^v, \quad z_{k,n} = z_k + nh_z^v, \quad 0 \leq l \leq N_x^v, \quad 0 \leq m \leq N_y^v, \quad 0 \leq n \leq N_z^v,$$

(see Figure 2(b)) with mesh sizes

$$h_x^v := \frac{h_x}{N_x^v}, \quad h_y^v := \frac{h_y}{N_y^v}, \quad h_z^v := \frac{h_z}{N_z^v}.$$

2.2.2 The Effective Thermomechanical Properties of the Material in a Subcuboid

The effective properties of the material in each subcuboid $V_{i,l,j,m,k,n} := [x_{i,l}, x_{i,l+1}] \times [y_{j,m}, y_{j,m+1}] \times [z_{k,n}, z_{k,n+1}]$ ($0 \leq l < N_x^v$, $0 \leq m < N_y^v$, $0 \leq n < N_z^v$) are approximated in turn. The composite is assumed to be void-free and locally unidirectional in such a subcuboid. The centroid $(x_{i,l+\frac{1}{2}}, y_{j,m+\frac{1}{2}}, z_{k,n+\frac{1}{2}})$ of the subcuboid lies either in a yarn (Figure 2(c)(ii)) or in the resin (Figures 2(c),(i)&(iii)).

Figure 2: Each voxel $V_{i,j,k}$ (coloured yellow) is subdivided into N_v cuboids $V_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$, and if the centroid $(x_{i,l+\frac{1}{2}}, y_{j,m+\frac{1}{2}}, z_{k,n+\frac{1}{2}})$ of $V_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ (coloured blue) lies in a yarn (top view in (c)(ii) with resin, yarn coloured grey, white respectively), then $V_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ is sampled at N_m points distributed on a uniform mesh (see (d)).

If it lies in the resin, the fourth order stiffness tensor and second order coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) tensors of the material in the subcuboid are approximated to be those of the resin:

$$C_{i,l,j,m,k,n} = C^{\text{resin}}, \quad \alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n} = \alpha^{\text{resin}}.$$

If the centroid lies in a yarn then to approximate the fibre volume fraction of the material in the subcuboid, it is sampled at $N_m = N_x^m N_y^m N_z^m$ points

$$x_{i,l,p} = x_{i,l} + \left(p + \frac{1}{2}\right) h_x^m, \quad y_{j,m,q} = y_{j,m} + \left(q + \frac{1}{2}\right) h_y^m, \quad z_{k,n,r} = z_{k,n} + \left(r + \frac{1}{2}\right) h_z^m, \\ 0 \leq p < N_x^m, \quad 0 \leq q < N_y^m, \quad 0 \leq r < N_z^m,$$

(see Figure 2(d)) where

$$h_x^m := \frac{h_x^v}{N_x^m}, \quad h_y^m := \frac{h_y^v}{N_y^m}, \quad h_z^m := \frac{h_z^v}{N_z^m}.$$

Since the subcuboid can be partitioned into regions centred at the grid points

$$V_{i,l,j,m,k,n} = \bigcup_{p,q,r} \left[x_{i,l,p-\frac{1}{2}}, x_{i,l,p+\frac{1}{2}} \right] \times \left[y_{j,m,q-\frac{1}{2}}, y_{j,m,q+\frac{1}{2}} \right] \times \left[z_{k,n,r-\frac{1}{2}}, z_{k,n,r+\frac{1}{2}} \right],$$

each of which has volume $h_x^m h_y^m h_z^m$, the fibre volume fraction of the material in the subcuboid is approximately

$$V_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{(f)} = \frac{h_x^m h_y^m h_z^m}{h_x^v h_y^v h_z^v} \sum_{p,q,r} \delta(x_{i,l,p}, y_{j,m,q}, z_{k,n,r}) = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{p,q,r} \delta(x_{i,l,p}, y_{j,m,q}, z_{k,n,r}),$$

where $h_x^v h_y^v h_z^v$ is the volume of the subcuboid and

$$\delta(x_{i,l,p}, y_{j,m,q}, z_{k,n,r}) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } (x_{i,l,p}, y_{j,m,q}, z_{k,n,r}) \text{ is in a yarn,} \\ 1 & \text{if } (x_{i,l,p}, y_{j,m,q}, z_{k,n,r}) \text{ is in the resin.} \end{cases}$$

A micromechanics model such as the thermomechanical one of Chamis [4], or the elastic model of Hashin [5] together with the thermal model of Chamberlain [6], is used to approximate the thermomechanical properties

$$E_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},1}, \quad E_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},2} = E_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},3}, \quad G_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},12} = G_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},31}, \quad G_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},23}, \\ \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},12} = \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},13}, \quad \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},23} = \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},32}, \quad \alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},11}, \quad \alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},22} = \alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},33}$$

of the composite material in the subcuboid. Here 1 denotes the fibre direction and 2, 3 denote the transverse directions, see Figure 3. The assumed orthotropy of the material in the subcuboid with respect to the local material coordinates gives

$$\nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},31} = \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},21} = \frac{E_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},2} \nu_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},12}}{E_{i,l,j,m,k,n}^{\text{comp},1}}.$$

Figure 3: Local material coordinates in a subcuboid.

The standard elasticity theory for orthotropic materials [7] gives the fourth order stiffness and second order CTE tensors, $\tilde{C}_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ respectively, of the material in the subcuboid with respect to local coordinates; and standard tensor transformations give the corresponding tensors $C_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ and $\alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ with respect to global (x, y, z) coordinates.

2.2.3 The Effective Thermomechanical Properties of the Material in the Voxel

The effective stiffness tensor $C_{i,j,k}$ of the material in the voxel $V_{i,j,k}$ is taken to be the average of the stiffness tensors for the subcuboids:

$$C_{i,j,k} = \frac{h_x^v h_y^v h_z^v}{h_x h_y h_z} \sum_{l,m,n} C_{i,l,j,m,k,n} = \frac{1}{N_v} \sum_{l,m,n} C_{i,l,j,m,k,n}, \quad (1a)$$

where $h_x^v h_y^v h_z^v$ is the volume of each subcuboid and $h_x h_y h_z$ is the volume of the voxel. To find the effective CTE vector $\beta_{i,j,k}$ corresponding to the tensor $\alpha_{i,j,k}$ of the material in $V_{i,j,k}$, the average of the thermal stress vectors in the subcuboids is pre-multiplied by the effective compliance matrix of the material in $V_{i,j,k}$:

$$\beta_{i,j,k} = D_{i,j,k}^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{N_v} \sum_{l,m,n} D_{i,l,j,m,k,n} \beta_{i,l,j,m,k,n} \right), \quad (1b)$$

where $D_{i,j,k}$, $D_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ are the matrices corresponding to $C_{i,j,k}$, $C_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ respectively and $\beta_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$ is the vector corresponding to $\alpha_{i,l,j,m,k,n}$. This approach is taken as the straightforward averaging of the CTE tensors for the subcuboids does not ensure that the correct thermal stresses are applied within the finite element calculations.

2.3 The Effective Thermomechanical Properties of the Bulk Material

The material in the RVE is modelled as being homogeneous in each voxel $V_{i,j,k}$, with stiffness tensor and CTE vector given by equations (1).

To find the effective material properties, FEAs are used to find the stresses which result from applying normal and shear loads, and the strains which result from applying a unit temperature change, to this locally homogeneous material under suitable periodic boundary conditions.

The boundary conditions are discussed in Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, and the determination of the effective thermomechanical properties is examined in Section 2.3.3.

2.3.1 The Elastic Periodic Boundary Conditions

Only normal and shear forces in the xy -plane are discussed here; the other forces are treated analogously. The displacements of the nodes are related by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) - \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_j, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) - \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), \\ \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) - \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{ref} , \mathbf{y}_{ref} and \mathbf{z}_{ref} are non-structural (or fictitious) nodes which connect corresponding nodes on opposite x , y and z faces respectively.

To apply the normal strain in the x -direction, one of the corner nodes is fully fixed to prevent translational motion:

$$\mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_0) = \mathbf{0},$$

and a unit displacement is applied to \mathbf{x}_{ref} in the x -direction with \mathbf{y}_{ref} and \mathbf{z}_{ref} fully fixed:

$$\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}) = (1, 0, 0)^T, \quad \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}) = \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (3)$$

So the boundary conditions (2) simplify to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{0}, \\ \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = (1, 0, 0)^T, \\ \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_j, z_k) + (1, 0, 0)^T, \quad \forall (j, k) \neq (0, 0), (N_y, 0), (0, N_z), (N_y, N_z), \\ \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_k), \quad \forall (i, k) \neq (0, 0), (N_x, 0), (0, N_z), (N_x, N_z), \\ \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_0), \quad \forall (i, j) \neq (0, 0), (N_x, 0), (0, N_y), (N_x, N_y), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{d} = (u, v, w)^T$, i.e. u , v and w are the displacement of a node in the x , y and z directions respectively. However, these boundary conditions are not linearly independent:

$$\mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_0), \quad 0 < i < N_x,$$

i.e. the nodes (x_i, y_{N_y}, z_0) , (x_i, y_0, z_0) , (x_i, y_0, z_{N_z}) and (x_i, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) are related in a closed loop, as are the nodes

$$\begin{aligned} (x_{N_x}, y_j, z_0), (x_0, y_j, z_0), (x_0, y_j, z_{N_z}) &\text{ and } (x_{N_x}, y_j, z_{N_z}), & 0 < j < N_y \\ (x_{N_x}, y_0, z_k), (x_0, y_0, z_k), (x_0, y_{N_y}, z_k) &\text{ and } (x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_k), & 0 < k < N_z. \end{aligned}$$

So a necessary and sufficient set of boundary conditions is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{0}, \\ \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_0) = \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = (1, 0, 0)^T, \\ \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_j, z_k) + (1, 0, 0)^T, \quad \forall j, k > 0 : (j, k) \neq (N_y, N_z), \\ \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_k), \quad \forall i \geq 0, k > 0 : (i, k) \neq (0, N_z), (N_x, N_z), \\ \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_0), \quad \forall (i, j) \neq (0, 0), (N_x, 0), (0, N_y), (N_x, N_y). \end{aligned}$$

To apply an xy -shear, the unit displacement of \mathbf{x}_{ref} in (3) is replaced by one in the y direction, and an additional unit displacement is applied to \mathbf{y}_{ref} in the x -direction:

$$\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}) = (0, 1, 0)^T, \quad \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}) = (1, 0, 0)^T, \quad \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (4)$$

In this case, a necessary and sufficient set of boundary conditions is

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) = \mathbf{0}, & \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_{N_z}) = (0, 1, 0)^T, \\
\mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = (1, 0, 0)^T, \\
\mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= \mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}) = (1, 1, 0)^T, \\
\mathbf{d}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_0, y_j, z_k) + (0, 1, 0)^T, & \forall j, k > 0 : (j, k) &\neq (N_y, N_z), \\
\mathbf{d}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_0, z_k) + (1, 0, 0)^T, & \forall i \geq 0, k > 0 : (i, k) &\neq (0, N_z), (N_x, N_z), \\
\mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) &= \mathbf{d}(x_i, y_j, z_0), & \forall (i, j) &\neq (0, 0), (N_x, 0), (0, N_y), (N_x, N_y).
\end{aligned}$$

It is actually sufficient to apply either one of the unit displacements in (4) on its own while keeping the other two fictitious nodes fully fixed. In either case, a similar set of necessary and sufficient set of boundary conditions to the one above can be found.

2.3.2 The Thermal Periodic Boundary Conditions

The unit temperature change $\Delta T = 1$ is applied to the material in the RVE. As in Section 2.3.1, one of the corner nodes is fully fixed to prevent translational motion:

$$\mathbf{d}(x_0, y_0, z_0) = \mathbf{0}.$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}) &= (u(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), v(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), w(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}))^T, & \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}) &= (u(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), v(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), w(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}))^T, \\
\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}) &= (u(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), v(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), w(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}))^T,
\end{aligned}$$

the boundary conditions (2) simplify to

$$\begin{aligned}
u(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= u(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= v(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= w(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), \\
u(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= u(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= v(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= w(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), \\
u(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= u(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= v(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= w(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) &- \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_0, y_j, z_k) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & j+k > 0, \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) &- \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_0, z_k) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & i+k > 0, \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) &- \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_j, z_0) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & i+j > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

However, as in Section 2.3.1, these boundary conditions are not linearly independent because the nodes

$$\begin{aligned}
(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_0), & (x_i, y_0, z_0), & (x_i, y_0, z_{N_z}) & \text{ and } & (x_i, y_{N_y}, z_{N_z}), & 0 < i \leq N_x \\
(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_0), & (x_0, y_j, z_0), & (x_0, y_j, z_{N_z}) & \text{ and } & (x_{N_x}, y_j, z_{N_z}), & 0 < j \leq N_y \\
(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_k), & (x_0, y_0, z_k), & (x_0, y_{N_y}, z_k) & \text{ and } & (x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, z_k), & 0 < k \leq N_z
\end{aligned}$$

are related in closed loops. So a necessary and sufficient set of boundary conditions is

$$\begin{aligned}
u(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= u(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= v(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_{N_x}, y_0, z_0) &= w(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), \\
u(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= u(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= v(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_0, y_{N_y}, z_0) &= w(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), \\
u(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= u(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & v(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= v(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & w(x_0, y_0, z_{N_z}) &= w(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_{N_x}, y_j, z_k) - \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_0, y_j, z_k) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}}), & j, k > 0, \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_{N_y}, z_k) - \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_0, z_k) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}}), & k > 0, \\
\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_j, z_{N_z}) - \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(x_i, y_j, z_0) &= \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix}(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}}), & i + j > 0.
\end{aligned}$$

2.3.3 Determining The Effective Thermomechanical Properties of the Bulk Composite

As in Section 2.3.1, only normal and shear forces in the xy -plane are discussed here; the other forces are treated analogously. Firstly, consider normal loading of the effective material in the x -direction. The resulting nodal stresses are denoted by $\{\sigma_x^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$, $\{\sigma_y^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$, $\{\sigma_z^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$, $\{\sigma_{xy}^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$, $\{\sigma_{yz}^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$ and $\{\sigma_{xz}^{i,j,k}\}_{i,j,k}$, and the respective average values by $\bar{\sigma}_x$, $\bar{\sigma}_y$, $\bar{\sigma}_z$, $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$, $\bar{\sigma}_{yz}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\sigma}_x &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_x^{i,j,k}, & \bar{\sigma}_y &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_y^{i,j,k}, & \bar{\sigma}_z &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_z^{i,j,k}, \\
\bar{\sigma}_{xy} &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_{xy}^{i,j,k}, & \bar{\sigma}_{yz} &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_{yz}^{i,j,k}, & \bar{\sigma}_{xz} &= \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i,j,k} \sigma_{xz}^{i,j,k},
\end{aligned}$$

where $P := (N_x + 1)(N_y + 1)(N_z + 1)$ is the number of nodes. The effective material strain is taken to be the x -strain of the fictitious node \mathbf{x}_{ref} introduced in Section 2.3.1:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{x_t - x_b},$$

and the *effective material stiffness matrix* D is taken to satisfy

$$(\bar{\sigma}_x, \bar{\sigma}_y, \bar{\sigma}_z, \bar{\sigma}_{yz}, \bar{\sigma}_{xz}, \bar{\sigma}_{xy})^T = (D_{11}, D_{21}, D_{31}, D_{41}, D_{51}, D_{61})^T \bar{\epsilon}_x.$$

Consider applying an xy -shear, and let $\bar{\sigma}_x$, $\bar{\sigma}_y$, $\bar{\sigma}_z$, $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}$, $\bar{\sigma}_{yz}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}$ denote the resulting average nodal stresses. The effective material shear is taken to be

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{xy} = \frac{1}{x_t - x_b} + \frac{1}{y_t - y_b},$$

and D is taken to satisfy

$$(\bar{\sigma}_x, \bar{\sigma}_y, \bar{\sigma}_z, \bar{\sigma}_{yz}, \bar{\sigma}_{xz}, \bar{\sigma}_{xy})^T = (D_{16}, D_{26}, D_{36}, D_{46}, D_{56}, D_{66})^T \bar{\epsilon}_{xy}.$$

The remaining entries of D are populated similarly: the second and third columns $\{D_{i2}\}_i$ and $\{D_{i3}\}_i$ arise from normal loading of the effective material in the y - and z -directions respectively, and the fourth and fifth columns $\{D_{i4}\}_i$ and $\{D_{i5}\}_i$ arise from applying yz - and xz -shears to the effective material respectively.

Certain weave patterns, including plain weave, 2×2 twill and 5-harness satin weave, are invariant under the transformation $x \leftrightarrow y$ up to reflection in the x or y axis. It is readily seen that as well as being symmetric, the effective material stiffness matrix of a lamina reinforced with such a material should satisfy $D_{11} = D_{22}$, $D_{13} = D_{23}$ and $D_{44} = D_{55}$, and the relevant entries of D are redefined to reflect this:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D_{11} + D_{22}}{2} &\rightarrow D_{11}, D_{22}, \frac{D_{12} + D_{21}}{2} \rightarrow D_{12}, D_{21}, D_{33} \rightarrow D_{33}, \\ \frac{D_{13} + D_{32} + D_{23} + D_{32}}{4} &\rightarrow D_{13}, D_{32}, D_{23}, D_{32}, \frac{D_{44} + D_{55}}{2} \rightarrow D_{44}, D_{55}, D_{66} \rightarrow D_{66}, \\ D_{ij} &= 0 \text{ otherwise.} \end{aligned}$$

The standard elasticity theory for orthotropic materials [7] gives the effective material properties $E_x = E_y$, E_z , G_{xy} , $G_{xz} = G_{yz}$, $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx}$ and $\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$, and the orthotropy of the material gives that $\nu_{zy} = \nu_{zx} = \frac{E_z \nu_{xz}}{E_x}$.

The effective CTEs are found from the strains of the fictitious nodes \mathbf{x}_{ref} , \mathbf{y}_{ref} and \mathbf{z}_{ref} introduced in Section 2.3.2:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\alpha}_x &= \frac{u(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}})}{x_t - x_b}, \bar{\alpha}_y = \frac{v(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}})}{y_t - y_b}, \bar{\alpha}_z = \frac{w(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}})}{z_t - z_b}, \bar{\alpha}_{xy} = \frac{v(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}})}{y_t - y_b} + \frac{u(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}})}{x_t - x_b}, \\ \bar{\alpha}_{xz} &= \frac{w(\mathbf{x}_{\text{ref}})}{z_t - z_b} + \frac{u(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}})}{x_t - x_b}, \bar{\alpha}_{yz} = \frac{w(\mathbf{y}_{\text{ref}})}{z_t - z_b} + \frac{v(\mathbf{z}_{\text{ref}})}{y_t - y_b}. \end{aligned}$$

3. MODEL VALIDATION

In this section, the predicted thermomechanical properties of a Hexcel 8552/AS4 193gsm plain weave lamina with a fibre volume fraction of 55% are compared to measured values given in [8], which contains validation data used in the DTI-funded Precimould+ project. The fibre and resin properties are given in Table 1. The Hashin [5] elastic and Chamberlain [6] (with hexagonal packing) thermal models are used for the micromechanical modelling, $N = 20 \times 20 \times 8$ voxels are used, each voxel is divided into $N_v = 6 \times 6 \times 6$ subcuboids, and if the centroid of a subcuboid lies in a yarn then the material in the subcuboid is sampled at $N_m = 6 \times 6 \times 6$ points to approximate its fibre volume fraction. The open source CalculiX software for windows [11] is used to perform the FEAs, and a comparison between the predicted and measured thermomechanical properties of the lamina is given in Table 2. Prediction of the Young's moduli is excellent (predicted values within 7% of experimental ones), prediction of the remaining elastic properties and the CTEs is also very good (differences of up to 22%) considering the likely experimental errors.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A unit cell method which uses voxel-based homogenization to predict the bulk thermomechanical properties of a woven fabric reinforced composite has been detailed, and good agreement with experimental data for a carbon/epoxy composite has been shown.

Table 1: Hexcel 8552 resin [9] & AS4 carbon fibre [10] thermomechanical properties

E^{resin} (MPa)	4670	$\nu_{01}^{\text{fibre}} = \nu_{02}^{\text{fibre}}$ (-)	0.2
ν^{resin} (-)	0.35	$G_{01}^{\text{fibre}} = G_{02}^{\text{fibre}}$ (MPa)	15000
α^{resin} ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	65	G_{12}^{fibre} (MPa)	7000
E_0^{fibre} (MPa)	225000	α_0^{fibre} ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	-0.5
$E_1^{\text{fibre}} = E_2^{\text{fibre}}$ (MPa)	15000	$\alpha_1^{\text{fibre}} = \alpha_2^{\text{fibre}}$ ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	15

Table 2: Predicted and Measured [8] Thermomechanical Properties of Lamina

	Pred. Value	Meas. Value	% Diff.		Pred. Value	Meas. Value	% Diff.
$E_x = E_y$ (MPa)	60902	61500	-0.97	$\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx}$ (-)	0.054996	0.05	9.99
E_z (MPa)	8412.8	9000	-6.52	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$ (-)	0.46288	0.5	-7.42
G_{xy} (MPa)	5229.5	4300	21.62	$\alpha_x = \alpha_y$ ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	3.1456	2.76	13.97
$G_{xz} = G_{yz}$ (MPa)	2931.4	2600	12.75	α_z ($\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	58.633	51.8	13.19

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